

Research methodology

Lyophilized blast (Bl) fungal mycelia are nonviable and suitable for international exchange

R. Scott, B. Consignado, R. Nelson, and R. Zeigler, IRRRI; and H. Leung, Plant Pathology Department, Washington State University, USA

In the study of populations of rice Bl fungus *Magnaporthe grisea* (anamorph *Pyricularia grisea*, *P. oryzae*), DNA fingerprinting based on restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) and randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) has proved highly informative. Plant pathologists studying Bl recognize the need to analyze populations of the fungus both regionally and worldwide. Unfortunately, relatively few institutions have the necessary resources to perform RFLP and RAPD assays. While collaboration with well-equipped laboratories for comparison of fungal populations seems the ideal solution to limited resources, concern about introducing nonindigenous strains of *M. grisea* into the region of the host

laboratory restricts exchange of fungal isolates.

Purified DNA is currently the only accepted material for international exchange among rice-growing regions. We determined that freeze-dried hyphae of Bl fungus are nonviable and can be safely exchanged instead of pure DNA. We tested the viability of intact lyophilized mycelia (84 samples) and ground lyophilized mycelia (58 samples) from different field strains of *M. grisea*. Hyphal plugs of *M. grisea* were started and grown on modified Fries medium (per liter: 30 g sucrose, 5 g ammonium tartrate, 1 g NH_4NO_3 , 1 g KH_2PO_4 , 0.5 g MgSO_4 , 0.1 g CaCl_2 , 0.1 g NaCl , 0.5 g yeast extract, and 0.5 g casein hydrolysate) dispensed in 50-ml volumes in 125- or 250-ml Erlenmeyer flasks. Flask cultures were shaken for a week at ambient temperature (28-30 °C) on a rotary platform moving at about 150 rpm. Mycelia were continuously submerged and agitated to prevent conidiation.

Mycelia were harvested by suction, rinsed with sterile distilled water, and lyophilized. Dried mycelia were pul-

verized manually under liquid nitrogen. Both intact and ground mycelia were then inoculated onto Fries medium and prune agar plate (per liter of prune infusion: 30-40 g prunes, 5 g lactose, 1 g yeast extract, and 20 g agar), and observed for fungal growth. None of the lyophilized mycelia incubated on either medium for 5 d at 30 °C initiated Bl fungal growth.

We conclude that freeze-dried fungal mycelia are nonviable and therefore suitable for international exchange. For shipment, we recommend that mycelia be packed individually in sterile coin packets and sealed collectively in evacuated plastic bags with activated silica gel or any suitable solid desiccant. Mycelial powders should be wrapped in greased or weighing sheets prior to packing in coin packets to avoid cross-contamination. If kept moisture-tight, mycelia can be stored and shipped at ambient temperatures for at least a week. For long-term storage, we suggest shelving samples at subzero temperatures. Blast researchers for whom DNA extraction is impractical should find the possibility of exchanging lyophilized mycelia particularly useful. ■

An empirical relationship between N input and false smut intensity in rice

Harkirat S. Dhindsa, Biological Science Department, Faculty of Health Sciences, The University of Sydney, Lidcombe, New South Wales 2141, Australia; and Harjinder S. Dhindsa, Regional Rice Research Station (RRRS) Kapurthala, Punjab, India

A strong correlation between N input and false smut (*Claviceps oryzae-sativae*) incidence has consistently been reported in the literature. An empirical model that quantitatively describes this relationship might assist in predicting the disease.

We conducted an experiment at RRRS, Punjab Agriculture University, Gudasapur, Punjab, to characterize this relationship. Data were recorded for rice cultivars PR109 and PR106, which were transplanted in 5- × 2-m plots. The experiment

Table 1. Observed (Obs) and predicted (Pred) percent incidence of false smut, RRRS, Punjab Agricultural University, Gurdaspur, Punjab, India.

Cultivar	Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Plants		Tillers		Grains	
		Obs	Pred	Obs	Pred	Obs	Pred
PR109	29	11.4	11.1	14.9	15.9	1.4	1.5
	92	16.2	16.9	22.7	20.9	3.3	3.0
	154	22.9	23.1	29.3	28.6	4.2	4.2
	217	30.5	29.6	36.3	39.0	4.7	5.0
	279	36.2	36.6	53.4	52.1	5.8	5.6
E			0.027		0.060		0.065
R ²			0.996		0.984		0.977
P			<0.01		<0.01		<0.01
PR106	29	8.6	8.9	12.8	12.8	1.3	1.3
	92	14.3	13.4	19.3	19.3	2.0	2.0
	154	18.1	18.5	24.8	24.9	2.5	2.5
	217	23.8	24.1	29.6	29.6	2.9	2.9
	279	30.5	30.3	33.5	33.5	3.2	3.2
E			0.035		0.002		0.006
R ²			0.996		1.0		1.0
P			<0.01		<0.01		<0.01